

TEACHING LISTENING WITH TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: The use of technology has become an increasingly popular method for enhancing the teaching of listening skills. By incorporating technology into the classroom, educators are able to provide a more interactive and engaging learning experience for students. With the help of various digital tools and resources, students are able to improve their listening abilities in an efficient and effective manner. This article will show that exploring the use of technology in enriching the instruction of listening skills. It underscores the diverse methods through which technology can be incorporated in language learning settings to enhance learners' comprehension capacities. Language teachers have long used technology to practice listening. From more traditional media such as analog audio and language labs to newer, Internet-based media, technology helps provide learners with authentic and realistic experiences that add excitement to the learning process and increase their contact with the language. The use of technology in the teaching of listening skills has proven to be an effective and efficient method for improving students' abilities.

Keywords: Technology, enhance, teaching listening, language learning, technology, technology-based media, songs, audio books, podcasts, english video, cartoon, film.

In our world today, technology has become a vital part of our life as it gives emphasis and clear understanding of how the world works today and how to cope up with the new and exciting society we have right now, especially in the school where most of the young and adult learners specifically students know more about the use of technology. Therefore, technology is widely used for its integration into the educational system. Listening is an important way of gaining access to information in the world today. Students can learn from listening resources on the internet by watching videos, listening to audio/podcasts, watching visuals, engaging in conversations, and reading transcripts/subtitles. To be a good teacher, you need to be a good listener. Active listening skills should be attended to, such as paying attention. People naturally tend to listen selectively because there is much to listen to and because of the possible external distractions like background noise and internal distractions like thinking about something else. Audio technology exposes students to a variety of speakers, voices, accents, situations, and rich cultural content, and it affords additional practice outside the classroom. It is easy to access and use at low or no cost. Not only does it save a teacher's energy and voice, it offers a listener a certain degree of control over listening. Whereas the real-life voice is gone once the words have been spoken, a recording can be paused and replayed as many times as needed to understand its meaning. Audio technology can add interest to language instruction in several ways. For example, a longer passage can be divided into man-ageable portions by pausing at natural breaks. A teacher can also pause listening to

ask students to predict what they might hear next, write an answer, transcribe a sentence, or simply repeat after the speaker for pronunciation practice. Recording parts of an audio segment separately can lead to an information-gap activity in which groups of students each listen to a part of the text and try to reconstruct the whole story together.

An abundance of listening materials available in many different formats makes it easy to find an appropriate text for any student population. Some technology-based activities primarily focus on listening and others naturally combine listening and speaking, but most of them extend to practice of other language skills and strategies. They are easy to sequence and integrate into any curriculum, can be adjusted depending on the level of language proficiency, and work well in or out of class. Following are the most popular and widely accepted teachers' choices that can be used to teach listening comprehension in a variety of classroom settings:

- songs
- audio books
- radio (e.g., Voice of America, BBC, CNN, and Spotlight Radio)
- listening websites for ESOL (e.g., The English Listening Lounge, Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab, English Language Listening Online, Daily ELS)
- video (e.g., commercials, documentaries, feature films, shows, and educational videos for native and nonnative speakers of English)
- podcasts (e.g., OhMyNews, ESL Podcast, and Breaking News English)
- academic lectures (e.g., iTunes University, Academic Earth, and MIT Open Courseware)

Technology-based media make teaching and learning more accessible and easy, to begin with. Future teachers should integrate this technology-based since it creates collaboration and enhances the students' listening skills; it raises awareness about the technology, and students can learn a lot from it and be creative on their own. Furthermore, future researchers should consider this technology-based media, which proves helpful. The purpose of this technology-based is to allow educators, readers, and researchers to consider this and make a way to integrate this into the education system. Many arguments talk about the integration of technology since it removes or lessens the old traditional way of teaching, yet most of them believe that it connects them to one with a common goal.

THE MAIN PART

Today, in order to learn foreign languages, it is recommended to study not only grammar but also basic skills equally. To improve your listening skills, many websites are ready for us to use openly today. For example, to develop listening and pronunciation, we can cite the following web pages as an example.

- Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab
- YouGlish
- News in levels

We can visit his other Web sites at DailyESL.com, EZslang.com, and

Trainyouraccent.com for more practice. Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab website provides a way for ESL students to improve their listening skills outside the classroom by providing autonomous learning materials. However, low-achieving students or those with limited computer skills use the tutor's instructions. Although the site includes "tests" for listening, the main purpose of the site is not to test students' listening ability; rather, students can explore ways to learn how to develop their listening skills by performing

a variety of pre-, post- and post-listening activities. This page has its own set of laws and regulations, and there is a huge amount of material available for use.

PODCAST

Using podcasts to develop listening skills A podcast is an audio file that a student or reader can download to their computer, phone, or mp3 player and listen to whenever they want. They are the best way to work on your or your students' listening skills. want. They are the best way to work on your or your students' listening skills because you can listen to them as much as you want. If you feel like an adventure, Because you can manipulate the files to make them run faster or slower, or just to listen to a part of the whole program. Podcasts now cover almost every topic you can think of. We can subscribe to nearly 30 series that cover topics such as science, movies, history, teaching, language and stories. There is something for everyone. You can find a list of some of my favorites and podcasts for English learners at <http://independentenglish.wordpress.com/podcasts>. Most podcasts are free and you can find them in a variety of ways. I find most of the podcasts I listen to on the BBC Podcasts page, the Apple Podcast app (which is automatically installed on Apple devices), or through the iTunes Podcasts tab, but just a search on Google will help you. For example, try a "movie review podcast" so you stay under the examples. Once you find a podcast you like, what can you do with it? As a student, do the following exercises: Read a brief summary of the podcast. Guess the three things the presenters are talking about. Listen and check. Choose ten words, phrases, or phrases that presenters will use. Play bingo. How many did you hear? If you listen to the same podcasts regularly, you will start to notice that the same phrases appear over and over again. Play two minutes of the podcast. Stop and then predict what you will hear. Keep listening. Are you right? Repeat this at several different points in the podcast. Listen to the full podcast without stopping. Record a summary of what you hear or record audio content. Listen again and see if you can add more information. Repetition improves your confidence. Choose a grammar like the current perfect that you want to improve. Focus on listening to it. How many times have you heard that? In what contexts is it used? Listen to the speaker and repeat. Whisper under your breath. Repeating this several times can help your pronunciation.

Watching videos

You can watch videos and read the subtitles on the internet. There has been increasing interest in pronunciation teaching and learning in parallel with recent developments in technology. Thanks to these developments, we have witnessed a number of applications and websites focusing on pronunciation. As Levis (2007) stated, computers can be utilized for individualized instruction, frequent practice through listening discrimination and focused repetition exercises, and automatic visual support. In this respect, YouGlish, a website which relies on YouTube videos to present target vocabulary through videos from a variety of genres, offers an invaluable resource for English language learners (ELLs) to improve their pronunciation.

CONCLUSION:

To sum up, nowadays technology plays a significant role, especially in the field of education in the teaching and learning process in the learning environment, that gives real and meaningful help in achieving the intended learning goals by using the appropriate technology-based media in the teaching and learning process. This paper, entitled

Technology-Based Media Used in Teaching Listening Skills: A Recent Literature Review, discussed the appropriate technology-based media that can make teachers' teaching effective and productive in teaching listening skills and lead the students to have productive growth and development in enhancing their listening skills. The technology-based media used in this paper are Mobile-Based Media, Multimedia Technology, Podcast Applications, Radio News, and Mobile-Based Audiobooks, which discuss and demonstrate the teaching and learning of listening skills to provide solutions to learning problems experienced by both teachers and students in learning listening skills. Technology has a great impact on student's skill related to listening. Besides that, there are so many opportunities to learn effectively.

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